

Generative Artificial Intelligence for Vulnerability Fixing in a Proprietary Software Ecosystem

Luiz Alexandre M. Costa^a, Awdren Fontão^b, Rodrigo Pereira dos Santos^a,
Alexander Serebrenik^c

^a*Federal University of the State of Rio de Janeiro (UNIRIO), Rio de Janeiro, Brazil*

^b*Federal University of Mato Grosso do Sul (UFMS), Campo Grande, Brazil*

^c*Eindhoven University of Technology (TU/e), Eindhoven, Netherlands*

DETAILS OF THE EXISTING SOFTWARE DEVELOPMENT PROCESS

This supplementary document provides a detailed description of the existing software development process used for vulnerability remediation prior to the introduction of the PSECO-SafePatch approach. The process, hereafter referred to as the “as-is” process, was analyzed as part of a participative case study conducted in a large global organization operating within a proprietary software ecosystem (PSECO).

In the context of the main study, our goal was to design and evaluate a GenAI-supported approach to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of vulnerability remediation, while preserving the delivery cadence in CI/CD pipelines. As such, the article primarily focuses on the proposed “to-be” process and its implementation. However, for transparency and reproducibility purposes, this document presents the structure, actors, steps, and limitations of the “as-is” process in detail.

The content is based on direct observations, internal documentation, and structured interviews conducted with development and security teams during the early stages of the case study. Understanding the baseline process is essential to contextualize the motivations for change, support the rationale behind our design decisions, and allow other researchers or practitioners to map similar challenges in their own environments.

This mapping highlights the existing flow of identifying, prioritizing, and fixing security vulnerabilities within CI/CD pipeline, as illustrated in Fig.1.

Figure 1: Existing (“as is”) CI/CD pipeline relating to vulnerability fix.

The activities of the existing (“as is”) CI/CD pipeline relating to vulnerability fix are detailed, as follows:

1. **Integrate Source Code Applications.** The process begins with the source code applications managed by Jenkins. Jenkins is an open-source automation server that facilitates CI/CD pipeline by automating the building, testing, and deployment of software projects. In this context, Jenkins orchestrates the process by managing the source code and triggering the next steps in the pipeline;
2. **Run Fortify Static Code Analyzer.** Once the source code is managed and processed by Jenkins, it is subjected to a security scan using Fortify Static Code Analyzer. Fortify is a tool that performs Static Application Security Testing (SAST) to identify vulnerabilities in the source code. It scans the codebase and generates a detailed list of vulnerabilities, highlighting potential security risks that need to be addressed. Fig.2 presents an executive summary of a security scan audit, indicating that the software asset analyzed has 220 low-priority issues and no critical, high, or medium-priority issues identified;

Executive Summary

This workbook is intended to provide all necessary details and information for a developer to understand and remediate the different issues discovered during the **████████████████████**-ssc scan project audit. The information contained in this workbook is targeted at project managers and developers.

This section provides an overview of the issues uncovered during analysis.

Figure 2: Executive summary report in Fortify Static Code Analyzer. The software asset name is obscured to protect sensitive information.

- 3. Generate List of Vulnerabilities.** The output of the Fortify scan is a list of identified vulnerabilities. The report includes details such as the type of vulnerability, its severity, and the specific location in the code where the issue was found. It is worth noting that the reports do not generate the required patch code. This information serves as input for the next step, as it guides the development team in prioritizing and addressing the most critical vulnerabilities first. Fig.3 shows a low-priority *SQL Injection* vulnerability in the *<name omitted>.java* file, specifically at line 650 within the *<name omitted>method*. The vulnerability is related to improper input validation and representation, with the vulnerability being associated with the use of the *prepareStatement()* function, as identified by the Fortify scan engine;
- 4. Engage Development Team.** Upon receiving the list of vulnerabilities, the responsibility for correction falls on the development team. The developers must immediately interrupt their ongoing projects to focus on fixing the vulnerabilities. The vulnerabilities are treated with high priority to prevent potential security incidents. The developers work under tight deadlines to ensure that each identified vulnerability is addressed and fixed;

